

ISic1445

I.Sicily inscription 1445

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Λυκίσφοῦ ἔ

2. μὴ Μιλίχιος

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285090

EDR 120814

EDCS 41300045

EDCS 64800270

PHI 175656

PHI 329930

Bibliography

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